

GOVERNMENT ATTENTION TO THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE
TOURISM SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. *The usage of social media is playing great role for tourism development in the era of Internet. The study pays attention to the state decrees on the social media use for promoting Uzbekistan tourism potential through social media platforms.*

Keywords. *Social media, internet, tourism, tourists, destination, travel, media tools, development, tourism potential, tourism products, service, marketing platforms.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the state pays great attention to the development of various types of tourism in order to effectively use the potential of all tourist destinations of Uzbekistan. The sale of these types of tourism is also carried out at the level of state policy. As of January 2024, there are 5.35 billion Internet users worldwide, which is 66.2% of the world's population according to current statistics. Additionally, 4.7 billion people or 62.3 percent of the world's population are social media users. As it can be seen from these indicators, at a time when more than half of the world's population uses the Internet, and at the same time social media, in the world of travel, the tourism potential of countries is highlighted through these media tools, and tourists visit these countries contributes to a further increase in the propensity to prescribe.

In order to improve the activity of the tourist destination of Uzbekistan on social media, promote individual tourist destinations, eliminate existing problems and develop additional measures, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 2023 "Rapid development of tourism potential of the Republic and In the "Roadmap" set out in Appendix 4a of the Resolution PD-135 "On additional measures to further increase the number of domestic and foreign tourists", the following was defined:

✓ To organize press-tours around the country for the leading publications, TV channels, and famous bloggers of the CIS countries and take measures to bring 500,000 tourists to Samarkand region.

✓ Promoting the tourism potential of our country in the countries of Southeast Asia and Europe through platforms that are widely used in China.

✓ Introduction of the procedure for covering the costs of advertising of the national tourism products and services of the Republic of Uzbekistan on internationally prestigious tourist and marketing platforms of the subjects of the tourism industry in the Republic (tour operators and business entities providing hotel services) in cooperation with the Ministry of Culture and Tourism.

✓ Introduction of the procedure for providing information to business entities and the general public, including through the global Internet network, about the work carried out at the expense of the funds of the Tourism Support Fund.

✓ Development of "Uzbekistan business card" and renewal of the tourism brand.

✓ To invite tour operators from promising countries to Uzbekistan and to hold "Road Show" and "B2B" meetings aimed at showing the tourism potential of our country and establishing cooperation with local tour operators, as well as strengthening tourism promotion through online travel platforms program development.

✓ The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regional and Tashkent city hokims, attracting tour operators and organizing "PR-center" branches.

The purpose of this decision is to maximize the promotion of Uzbekistan and its specific tourist destinations through social media, to use the existing potential effectively and to create new destinations and introduce them to the public. to achieve as much information as possible, at the same time, all this is supported by the state and relevant organizations.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PD-60 approved as Annex 1 "2022-2026 - by increasing the export potential of the republic" in goals 28, 35 of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2026, the export volume of the republic will reach 30 billion US dollars in 2026, including tourism, transport, information and communication, including software it is determined to increase the export of supplies and other services by 1.7 times or reach 4.3 billion US dollars, as well as to increase the number of foreign tourists visiting the republic to 9 million people and to implement a special program for the rapid development of tourism in the Bukhara region. We can see the practical result of this by creating a strong social media brand for Uzbekistan and its specific tourist destinations in order to further increase the awareness of foreign tourists about our country, study their travel requirements, and encourage them to travel to our country.

Another reason for the development of social media in the field of tourism is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-158 dated 11.09.2023 "Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy. It lists the goals planned to be achieved in our country by 2030, and the most important goal of ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth is to increase the number of tourists by creating ample conditions for the development of foreign and domestic tourism in Uzbekistan. In this, the following are listed among the planned

achievements by 20230:

❖ Increasing the number of foreign tourists to 15 million, and the number of tourists coming for pilgrimage tourism to 3 million.

❖ Establishing 30 large tourism clusters in the republic at the expense of attracting private investments, increasing the number of guest places by at least 2 times, building 25 ropeways in mountainous areas, increasing the number of tourism neighborhoods to 175.

❖ To increase the export of tourism services to 5 billion dollars, to increase the export of medical and educational tourism to 1.5 billion dollars per year.

❖ Introduction of the “Tax free” system for foreign tourists at all international airports for products purchased and cleared from the republic.

❖ Development of the national program “Masterpieces of Ancient History” and restoration of cultural heritage objects within its framework, establishment of “open-air museums” in monuments.

The practical result of this strategy, which is important for our country and planned to be implemented, cannot be imagined without the development of social media in the field of tourism. To increase the number of tourists by creating social media accounts of Uzbekistan and its individual tourist destinations, to increase the awareness of tourists about the destinations, to demonstrate the potential of tourism in our country by demonstrating the practical results of the goals set in the strategy, to use social media content for pilgrimage, medicine, education tourism, in addition, by enriching it with information about specific tourism services, by forming new concepts and impressions about our country among tourists, it is possible to achieve a further increase in the probability of their visit.

The attention given by our government to the use of social media in the field of tourism can be seen in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 12.01.2024 “On measures to sharply increase the flow of foreign tourists to the Republic and further accelerate domestic tourism”. According to it, a number of promotional activities are planned to be carried out through social media

platforms.

Conclusion. measures of tourism promotion by our state and the use of social media in tourism are becoming one of the main and urgent issues for our country.

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